

LEARNING IN AN AGE OF OPPORTUNITY: UNTOLD STORIES OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

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Learning in an Age of Opportunity: Untold Stories of Junior High School Learners with Special Needs

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Abstract

This study used a qualitative-narratological design to unfold the stories of three (3) junior high school learners with special needs at Polomolok National High School. Purposive sampling was utilized to choose the study participants and used an in-depth interview to gather the data needed. Findings of the study revealed the challenges learners with special needs faced, such as: academic and classroom-related struggles, inclusive environment and peer support, and teachers' adjustment. In terms of how they coped with the challenges, the following themes were generated: resilient and supportive community and adaptive learning strategies and communication. Lastly, the learners with special needs uttered that motivation, academic improvement, inclusive education, and collaboration are the insights they have gained from their experiences. Through the exploration of these narratives, this study can help reduce stigma and discrimination and promote a more positive and inclusive culture that values diversity and recognizes the contributions of all learners.

Keywords: *educational management, learners with special needs, inclusive classroom, qualitative narratology, philippines*

Introduction

The education of students with special needs has evolved significantly, transitioning from special education (SPED) to integrated education and then to inclusive education. Learners with special needs now meet inclusion requirements and participate in regular education programs alongside their peers. Despite the support provided by guidelines, policies, and programs, ordinary schools with an inclusive approach face numerous difficulties. Challenges persist, hindering efforts to advance inclusive education (Allam & Martin, 2021; Walsh, 2018).

Globally, there are almost 240 million impaired children, and their disabilities make it difficult for them to receive an education. These children, like others, aspire for their future and require quality education to reach their full potential. Unfortunately, they are often marginalized in policymaking, limiting their access to education and inhibiting their social, economic, and political participation. Prejudice, stigma and the reluctance of decision-makers to integrate disability into school programs perpetuate educational obstacles for these children (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund [UNICEF], 2023).

In the Philippine arena, the Department of Education (DepEd) promulgated a law about Inclusive education policy in DepEd Order No. 72 s. 2009. It specified Increasing Children's Participation Rate through Inclusive Education (DepEd, 2009). Additionally, there has been a move in Philippine schools to include high-quality inclusion in special education. The Special Education Act, the Philippine Senate Bill 3002, is under review (Muega, 2016).

As a mother and teacher in a local context, I can affirm that raising a special child demands extra attention. Teaching students with unique needs can be challenging without a willingness to adapt. While initially daunting, the challenges of raising a child with special needs also bring immense blessings and rewards. Witnessing the resilience of other exceptional children and their supportive parents is incredibly empowering.

Based on the extensive reading of related literature, I have found a few articles that tackled the stories and narratives about junior high school learners with special needs, especially in an inclusive classroom setting. Thus, it encouraged me to gather and understand the stories of learners with special needs within Polomolok National High School and find ways to sustain their courage and fortitude amidst challenges and difficulties. Moreover, this study could also become a basis for the concerned educational administrators to achieve a more inclusive environment with the country's existing definitions, policies, and programs for inclusive education.

Literature Review

2.1 Experiences of Learners with Special Educational Needs

Inclusive education is the integration of learners who have special needs in academic institutions. With the growing number of learners with special needs, there is a great demand for opportunities to welcome diversity inside the classroom. Despite the diversity of abilities within the learning environment, teachers and students shared a common educational goal: to learn. As a result, educational institutions have begun implementing programs that cater to each learner's needs, regardless of his abilities or disabilities. Research on the practical implementation of inclusive education has come chiefly from Middle Eastern nations; the Philippines has seen very little of this kind of study (Graham, 2020; Nunez & Rosales, 2021).

Besides, people and children with special needs and disabilities are often ignored in general; the COVID-19 pandemic has posed a particular challenge for them. This unfortunate situation is made worse because, during an emergency, their voices are even less likely to be heard. Because no one should be left behind in this crisis, government policies during the pandemic must include people with disabilities who also have their global rights. This article examines the laws of the Philippines regarding inclusive special education and the rights of learners. It also highlighted potential educational interventions to support the student's learning during the pandemic. It included suggestions on disaster preparedness laws, regulations, and services that should take into consideration the needs of disabled pupils in terms of education, social and emotional support, and mental health during the pandemic. Future studies should look at how children with disabilities used digital media throughout the pandemic and assess how well assistive technologies worked to meet the educational needs of those with impairments (García et al., 2022; Toquero, 2020).

Further, the primary education legislation emphasizes all students' inclusion and full participation in school, which is at the heart of the equity-based Finnish educational system. A significant factor supporting inclusive schools is the social participation of SEN children. Thus, the social participation experiences of SEN students show how inclusion policies function in practice. The study showed a high correlation between students' perceptions of social participation and their experiences in the classroom. Additionally, even though their feelings and experiences about the school environment were frequently negative, their inherent strengths shielded them from complete social isolation. According to the findings, we should actively improve learning settings to preserve student variety and encourage social interaction among all students if we want to establish inclusive schools. More collaborative learning spaces, student-centered pedagogy, and acknowledging each child's unique abilities are essential for creating an inclusive educational environment. These strategies ensure that all students receive the support they need to thrive academically and socially (Vetoniemi & Kärnä, 2021; Vuorinen et al., 2019).

Hence, a study investigated the lives of mainstreamed learners with special educational needs (LSENs), how they interact with people inside and outside the school, how they feel about participating in different events and activities, and how others can interact with them effectively. In contrast to inclusive education's goal of making students with special needs "included," physically and socially, in a typical academic class, some participants reported feeling socially isolated. Participants reported communication challenges because not all people or teachers know sign language. This study concluded that, besides the standard teacher or adviser, there should be another teacher for the LSENs (Garcia, 2019; Juvonen et al., 2019).

Additionally, adolescents classified as having an emotional disturbance (ED) education category have some of the most significant academic deficiencies, behavioral difficulties, and adverse life outcomes when compared to other qualifying groups. It is challenging for school staff to comprehend the demands of the diverse group of pupils labeled as ED because of their heterogeneous makeup. According to the results, participants had difficulties throughout school, except for the last two years. They mentioned having issues with mental health, peer interactions, and executive functioning. The participants claimed they felt generally good about themselves, their professors, and both. The participants indicated enthusiasm and apprehension about life after high school when it came to the future (Erickson, 2022)

Besides inadvertently leading to low self-esteem, which further contributes to poor academic achievement, the literature reveals that many students with special needs experience abuse, social isolation, discrimination, segregation, labeling, stigmatization, bullying, and violence from the people who should be supporting them. It is believed that changing the educational system to be more inclusive would help prevent prejudiced and discriminatory behaviors and attitudes toward students who have special needs. The significant findings show that inclusive education is employed at the research location, where teachers provide the aid required for specific students with special needs. Less fortunate, the studies also show that learners with special needs experience varying degrees of prejudice, abuse, segregation, labeling, and social injustice. Readers are given a window into their world and experiences through their actual experiences. It meant that society's perspectives on and treatment of students with special needs underwent a paradigm shift. The study demonstrates the wide range of complicated experiences that students with special needs traverse daily and highlights teachers' crucial responsibilities in their general learning, involvement, and growth (Earnshaw et al., 2018; Olamide, 2021).

Moreover, finding answers to the challenges that children with specific learning disabilities (SLD) confront in the classroom is a common theme in discussions concerning these individuals. However, the experiences these students have had with self-advocacy should given more attention. The results showed that, despite some self-awareness, the students had limited knowledge of their SLD conditions, traits, and rights; they tended to emphasize the negative aspects of themselves and their school experiences; they were able to communicate their needs and preferences to the school staff, but this communication was not always acknowledged; and they lacked leadership traits when speaking up for others. These results imply that SLD students at Turkish vocational high schools may not have the necessary self-advocacy abilities and are not doing an excellent job of speaking out for themselves and others (Chong et al., 2024; Koca et al., 2023)

2.2 Coping Mechanisms of Learners with Special Needs

Coping is how a person decides how to handle the current issue. As they belong in an inclusive environment, this can change depending on how they react to the conditions. The attitudes and actions of students, teachers, and the general school environment can have a favorable or lousy impact on these children's school experiences. However, educators who have a negative attitude toward students with disabilities frequently anticipate poor performance and unacceptable behavior from these kids (Llego, 2022; Bastart et al., 2021).

In the USA, students with learning disabilities (LD) are the second most common disability group among children and youth who receive the bulk of their education in inclusive classrooms, behind students with speech and language impairments. However, very few studies have discussed the viewpoints of students with LD. This lack of research is particularly evident for those who attend inclusive classrooms. Understanding their perspectives is crucial for improving educational practices. Incorporating their viewpoints can lead to more effective and inclusive teaching methods (Connor & Cavendish, 2020).

Also, children with special needs benefit from classroom diversity in terms of academic achievement and social skills. It also improves these children's academic self-esteem and critical thinking skills. When diversifying classrooms for children with special needs, it is essential to take an inclusive approach. This means creating environments where all students, regardless of their abilities, can learn together. By fostering inclusivity, we promote a supportive and enriching educational experience for every child. The value of cooperative work in promoting inclusive education, the range of approaches utilized to address the needs of all students, including those with special needs, and the collaboration needed between educators and special education needs specialists to put those approaches into practice (Para & Siddiqui, 2022; Perlado Lamo de Espinosa et al., 2021).

Moreover, developing a curriculum model and framework for the Transition Program, which is made for exceptional learners with intellectual and physical disabilities, is necessary. It discusses the foundation for the curriculum and suggests a curriculum creation approach for making a transition program appropriate and sensitive to the needs of the Filipino setting. Five learning areas are included in the curriculum framework of the proposed Transition Program Curriculum: care, enrichment, academic, livelihood, and pre-vocational. All of these subject areas aim to support and equip Filipino students with special education needs to pursue careers in business, continue their education, or lead fulfilling lives. y providing tailored educational opportunities, these programs help students achieve their personal and professional goals. Such initiatives are designed to cater to individual learning needs, ensuring that each student receives the necessary support and resources. This personalized approach enhances the likelihood of academic success and career advancement for participants (Adams, 2021; Pawilen et al., 2018)

In the Philippines, various strategies have been implemented to increase education access for children with special needs (CSNs). Collaboration among stakeholders will be critical in achieving a more inclusive environment with the country's existing definitions, policies, and programs for inclusive education. In particular, the ease of access to professional services, their availability, and the policies in place to resolve conflicts that may emerge while using these services will all play a role in CSNs' progress toward full inclusion. It critically analyzed how current practices, policies, and cultures affect how inclusive education professionals and other stakeholders collaborate (Basister & Valenzuela, 2021; Kilag et al., 2024).

Moreover, students must possess the information, life skills, media literacy, and learning abilities necessary for 21st-century learning. For kids with special needs, often known as special needs kids (SNS), the school curriculum incorporates technology tools and tactics to teach and learn strategies to accomplish these skills. Research indicates that students' low digital literacy skills make it challenging to handle their academics in the digital learning environment. Being literate is crucial to becoming an autonomous learner in the digital age. According to earlier research, digital literacy abilities have been linked to improved student performance. In terms of its application in special education schools, it found that the prepared digitalized materials strongly affected learning. Students indicated that these computer-based activities were enjoyable. (Deveci et al., 2023; Tohara, 2021).

In other words, parents must participate in their children's educational programs under the Individuals with Disabilities Education Improvement Act (IDEA). However, the act's execution requires a more significant effort from parents than participation—specifically, it expects advocacy. Parents and educators are expected to collaborate on educational decision-making for students with disabilities. While collegial relationships are intended in this process, partnerships are only sometimes formed because both parties may need help understanding each other's points of view. Parents may have one point of view, whereas educators may have another (Haley & Allsop, 2019; Rossetti et al., 2021).

Moreover, schools in Norway are expected to uphold the ideals associated with inclusive education. In Norway, the most frequent definition of inclusive education is multiple-oriented, meaning that inclusive education results from a diversity of beliefs, processes, and experiences. The experiences of the learning environment are vital for student well-being and learning. Students' experiences have yet to be extensively researched as a foundation for educational policy and practice. This is especially true for students with disabilities and those receiving special education (Haug, 2021)

Additionally, the development, dissemination, and strict implementation of special education in schools must continue. To effectively provide education for all students with special educational needs and disabilities, inclusive education strategies and approaches must coexist with essential special education strategies and approaches. Hence, the problems with implementing inclusion are compounded by the need for more empirical research on the effectiveness of inclusion and stakeholders' awareness of the details of special education regulations. It suggested that everyone involved have a thorough understanding of special education regulations, be able to discriminate and understand history, and adopt the exact definition, standards, and goals when putting inclusion programs into action (Francisco et al., 2020; Kauffman & Hornby, 2020).

Finally, to make inclusive education a reality, educators, families, and entire communities must gain knowledge and skills to effectively implement practices that ensure a child's presence in an inclusive classroom and that the child is learning, has friends, and feels they

belong.

Methodology

I used a qualitative-narratological research design to explore the untold stories of learners with special needs, as this approach allowed for an in-depth and nuanced examination of their experiences. Learners with specific educational needs might have encountered different challenges and experiences that needed to be better recognized and documented in previous studies. The qualitative narrative research design enables researchers to examine these experiences more thoroughly and holistically (Tomaszewski et al., 2020).

The qualitative narrative study approach calls for gathering and examining non-numerical data such as text, video, or audio to comprehend ideas, opinions, or experiences. Researchers use it to develop genuine research ideas or gain a comprehensive understanding of a subject. According to some sources, qualitative research focuses on finding the observer involved in the world's reality. Field notes, interviews, conversations, images, films, and self-reported memoranda are just a few ways it transforms the world into a collage of representations. At this point, qualitative research needed a naturalistic, interpretive lens to perceive the environment around us (Aspers & Corte, 2019; Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Furthermore, qualitative research is renowned for its adaptability and suppleness to shifting study goals and conditions. As per Mohajan and Mohajan (2022), qualitative research enables the investigator to remain receptive to novel perspectives, unforeseen findings, and emerging themes that may surface throughout the investigation. Standard iterative qualitative research methodologies allow the researcher to adjust their methodology or study questions in response to ongoing data analysis (Mohajan & Mohajan, 2022).

Notably, discussions of power, voice, and representation were common in qualitative research. According to Smith (2018), qualitative research aims to amplify the voices of underserved and excluded groups by challenging prevailing ideologies and hierarchies. It seeks to provide a platform for marginalized perspectives, contributing to broader social critique and understanding. Reflecting critically on their own biases and positionality, qualitative researchers usually work to ensure fairness by acknowledging and mitigating any personal biases that may influence their interpretations. They strive to accurately represent their participants' perspectives, aiming to capture the diversity of experiences and viewpoints within their research (Smith, 2018).

In particular, I employed narratology, which looks at the participant's tales to understand the event and extract meaning from it. Making meaning of the lives of individuals through their narratives is usually the primary goal of this approach. The respondent's perspective of the subject of the study is also a fundamental component of all qualitative investigations. In a narrative inquiry, I took on the role of storyteller. Qualitative research is, therefore, characterized by an element related to the personal experience (subjectivity to some) of the subject under study (Dhungana, 2022).

Furthermore, Johnson et al. (2019) stated that researchers evaluated narrative research data using thematic analysis to uncover themes and patterns and gain insights into individuals' experiences and viewpoints. The study frequently employed a combination of coding and categorizing techniques to identify significant themes and sub-themes in the data. They used an open coding method to discover key data themes and organize them into broader categories to better understand how the participants constructed their narratives and what these narratives revealed about their sense of self.

Also, narrative research was a qualitative approach focused on exploring and analyzing the stories or narratives of learners with special needs. It also involved collecting and analyzing data through the stories or personal experiences of the participants. The narratives collected could have been in the form of written or spoken accounts, and researchers typically used various techniques such as interviewing, observation, and document analysis to collect the data. Through the analysis of narratives, the researcher could have identified common themes and gained insights into the complex and subjective nature of learners with special needs experiences (Leko et al., 2021).

In addition, narratives are a traditional technique that has helped people organize their experiences. Studying experience through a narrative lens is known as narrative inquiry. Using the narrative inquiry approach and its aftermath can lead to several research problems. It is not an easy duty to represent and interpret the speech of another; one must do so with humility and respect. It looks at how important it is to follow the values of kindness, fairness, and respect when writing about people's lives and communities. This is done through critical consciousness, dialog, and an interpersonal lens to make sure the research is empowering the participants and assisting in their transformation (Azzahrawi, 2021)

Furthermore, narratology is an appropriate research design for researching learners with special needs since it focused on story analysis, narratives, and storytelling. In this context, the tales that students with special needs talked about their experiences in an inclusive classroom setting could provide valuable insights into the challenges, opportunities, and methods they have employed to handle their varied roles. Moreover, the complexity and variety of learners' experiences may have been captured through narrative research. This strategy have brought to light subtleties that quantitative approaches would have missed (De Fina, 2021).

In summary, narratology was suitable for this academic endeavor as it only aimed to narrate and analyze the various untold stories of the participants, who were learners with special educational needs. Moreover, narratology was convenient as it allowed a qualitative investigation, requiring only a few participants.

Purposive sampling was utilized to choose the study participants. According to Sarfo et al. (2021), purposive sampling is an approach based on prior knowledge about a population and the objective of the research study, in which the researcher utilizes personal judgment to determine the sample. For theoretical saturation, researchers selected three (3) junior high school learners with special needs from Polomolok National High School as participants during the 2023-2024 school year.

As for the participants, they shared their stories about beginning, middle, and ending as learners with special needs in an inclusive classroom setting. Their beginning stories focused on the challenges they faced. On the other hand, middle stories elaborated on their coping mechanisms for the challenges they encountered, and ending stories revealed the insights or the lessons they had learned along their journey in an inclusive classroom environment.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the research question, derived from data gathered from in-depth interviews. It examines learners' narratives of their struggles, coping strategies, and insights, referred to as their beginning, middle, and ending stories, as learners with special needs in an inclusive classroom setting.

Table 1. *Stories of Junior high school Learners with Special needs in school*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Challenges	
Dual nature and environment of the school	
Adjustment for someone with impairment/needs	Academic and Classroom-Related Struggles
Limited resources and equipment	
Lacks accommodation for learners with special needs	
Feels the support of peers	
Help and encouragement of teachers	
Teachers' willingness to aid students	Inclusive Environment and Peer support
Classmates provide substantial support	
Allowing for full participation in activities	
Support system for academic endeavors	
Classroom management issues of teachers	Teachers' Adjustment
Unpreparedness in dealing with special needs	
Coping Mechanisms	
Facing challenges with positivity	
Finding support from understanding individuals	Resilient and Supportive Community
Teachers' and classmates' support brings joy	
Teachers help boost confidence	
Blind student utilizes Braille	
Cellphone for YouTube learning	Adaptive Learning Strategies and Communication
TV for lesson understanding	
Open communication with the teacher	
Insights	
Motivated to work harder in studies	Motivation and Academic Improvement
Focus on following instructions	
Doing one's best to improve the reading skills	
Schools become more accommodating	
Encouraging open communication and understanding	
Enhancing lesson comprehension with others	Inclusive Education and Collaboration
Necessitating dialogue with school authorities	
Support and understanding of the School Officials	

The in-depth interviews with learners with special needs provided a profound understanding of their diverse experiences within the inclusive education framework. These interviews unearthed a spectrum of challenges faced by these individuals, illustrating the multifaceted nature of their journey toward overcoming obstacles. These learners showcased remarkable resilience and determination in overcoming various challenges in pursuing effective inclusive education. Their experiences highlighted several key insights and recommendations that they were eager to impart to their peers with special needs, fostering a supportive and inclusive educational environment.

Moreover, the interviews provided a platform for these learners to share their experiences, strategies, and aspirations. Their insights and recommendations are a significant guide for fostering a more inclusive educational environment, ensuring that the needs of all learners, especially those with special needs, are met effectively.

4.1 Academic and Classroom-Related Struggles

This theme suggests that participants had resilience and determination to embrace the educational journey, even in the face of obstacles. It emphasized the participants' determination, dedication, and unwavering commitment to achieve academic success despite all

challenges. It was a tribute to their unbreakable spirit. Fostering valued relationships between peers and teachers creates an environment where students feel appreciated, understood, and encouraged in their academic pursuits. These positive interactions can inspire and motivate students, instilling hope and confidence in their ability to overcome challenges and achieve academic success.

According to Vetoniemi and Kärnä (2021), considering that their feelings and experiences about the school environment were frequently negative, their inherent strengths shield them from complete social isolation. Individuals with innate qualities are frequently strong in the face of hardship, even when confronted with constant negativity in the school environment. These characteristics could take many forms, including emotional intelligence, creativity, and problem-solving abilities. For example, students who excel at creativity may find consolation in expressing themselves via art or writing, allowing them to traverse the hurdles of the school environment more quickly. Similarly, someone with high emotional intelligence may be knowledgeable about their feelings and capable of controlling them, enabling them to preserve a sense of self amid unfavorable situations.

4.2 Inclusive Environment and Peer Support

This subject emphasizes the value of cooperation and assistance between individuals in conquering obstacles. Students can stay up with the academic pace when their peers are ready to help when they ask for it. This conduct highlights the significant benefits of a robust and supportive classroom community, where everyone's capacity to achieve was enhanced by their willingness to work together and support one another. The focus lies in highlighting the power of collaboration, creating an atmosphere where students are self-directed learners and engaged contributors to each other's academic pursuits.

Moreover, Koca et al. (2023) stated that children often struggle to comprehend and advocate for themselves in school due to their unique learning difficulties, characteristics, and rights. Although they showed signs of self-awareness, their focus on the negative aspects of their school experiences exacerbated their problems. Thus, these perspectives supported by Sender et al. (2024), who state that in addition to suppressing their unpleasant emotions, they frequently exhibit emotional instability. Aggressive reactions frequently linked to their bad attitudes.

4.3 Teachers' Adjustment

The theme revolves around the experiences of a student with a disability on entering a classroom, where the teacher initially struggled to comprehend and accommodate this unique situation. The importance of creating a welcoming and supportive environment in the classroom where children with disabilities are made to feel appreciated, understood, and included. This inclusivity benefits the individual student and enriches the overall educational experience for everyone within the classroom community.

According to the study results of Sharma et al. (2019), the participants identified several significant challenges that prevented those with disabilities from receiving help and inclusion in their communities. The absence of teacher preparation was one major obstacle. Insufficient training regarding the proper assistance and accommodations for students with disabilities may challenge educators to offer suitable learning settings and resources. Students may get frustrated and disengaged, making it harder for them to access high-quality education. Also, a study by Gesel et al. (2022) points out that teachers of students with disabilities assessed the sufficiency of access to support as somewhat insufficient to somewhat adequate, with the lowest scores for planning/release time and training/information. Teachers reported having greater access to collaboration than professional development. Academic intervention resources were obtained from colleagues, while nonacademic intervention resources came from administrators.

4.4 Resilience and Supportive Community

The theme embraces challenges, especially when these were part of regular classes for learners with disabilities and highlighted the importance of supportive relationships in promoting an inclusive learning environment. It underscores the dedication of learners with disabilities and stresses the need to understand, develop empathy for, and show sincere concern for individuals facing difficulties in educational settings. Meaningful involvement with community leaders and stakeholders is critical for increasing knowledge, raising awareness, and speaking up in support of the interests and rights of those with disabilities. Efforts to address systemic issues and adopt inclusive policies may be improved if major community decision-makers and influencers actively participate.

According to Hickey (2023), developing reliable relationships between students and teachers is crucial for student support. Trust and respect fostered when students feel personally connected to their teachers, enhancing their overall well-being and academic achievement. These deep connections, built on open communication, empathy, and understanding, go beyond the conventional student-teacher dynamic. Students who feel comfortable approaching their teachers with concerns, asking for assistance, and participating fully in the learning process are more likely to build these connections, resulting in increased support, motivation, and a sense of community within the classroom. As Weiss et al., (2018) noted, a healthy and effective learning environment is rooted in positive interactions between teachers and students. Building an atmosphere of appreciation, openness, and hope helps develop mutual respect and trust. Teachers with a grateful attitude acknowledge and value each student's unique abilities and contributions, fostering a sense of openness that encourages students to communicate their thoughts, express themselves, and have deep discussions.

4.5 Adaptive Learning Strategies and Communication

The theme focuses on how creatively learners with special needs use technology and adaptive learning strategies to participate in their

education. It emphasizes their dedication and resourcefulness, showcasing their innovative use of adapted techniques and technology to create inclusive, personalized learning environments that meet various learning requirements.

According to Tohara (2021), integrating media literacy, knowledge, and life skills into the curriculum is essential for preparing students for the challenges of the twenty-first century. Media literacy equips students to navigate and evaluate the vast amount of information in today's digital environment, including evaluating media messages and distinguishing reliable sources. Knowledge acquisition involves interdisciplinary skills applicable to real-world situations. Furthermore, study by Deveci et al. (2023) and other pertinent studies emphasize the digital resources that have been produced and have a substantial impact on learning when used in special education settings. The computer-based activities were well appreciated by the students. Moreover, Olamide (2021) stated that students with special needs face many challenging situations in everyday life involving behavioral, emotional, cognitive, or physical impairments that require specific assistance and modifications for equitable access to education. These students often need individualized learning plans and strategies tailored to their unique situations, from managing sensory sensitivities to addressing specific learning needs. Social and emotional challenges related to acceptance, belonging, and self-worth can further complicate their educational experiences.

4.6 Motivation and Academic Improvement

This theme highlights the individual's commitment to personal growth and academic improvement despite facing challenges. It emphasizes the determination to progress further in studies, highlighting the additional effort required due to the encountered challenges. The theme celebrates the unwavering commitment and determination of the individual in the face of challenges. It highlights the transformative power of perseverance and dedication in fostering personal growth, academic advancement, and the development of essential life skills necessary for success.

According to Ainscow's (2020) study, it is essential to understand that recognizing the resources and obstacles faced by students with special needs is a more complex strategy than just gathering evidence. These students face many kinds of difficulties that may be physical, cognitive, emotional, or social. Identifying issues and choosing the best solutions and support services can be easier by using assessments and evaluations based on empirical research. Assessments of behavior, social skills, academic achievement, adaptive functioning, and specific learning requirements may be included in this process. These evaluations provide a comprehensive understanding of each student's unique needs and strengths.

Moreover, Murdoch et al. (2020) stated that specific interactions between teachers and students are essential to creating learning settings where every student can access high-quality educational opportunities, and productive struggle is a crucial component of transformative learning processes. The definition of these relationships is "educational relationships that support students to feel heard." The authors begin by examining the idea of productive struggle, go over the three prerequisites that must met to foster these relationships, and then make links between the difficulties teachers encounter in fostering these supportive environments and the outcomes that students experience.

4.7 Inclusive Education and Collaboration

This theme emphasizes the importance of fostering open communication between educators and school administrators to address the requirements of students with special needs effectively. It underscores its pivotal role in creating a friendly, inclusive classroom setting that meets the needs of unique requirements of these learners, promoting equitable opportunities for all students to thrive academically.

According to Francisco et al. (2020) and Kauffman and Hornby (2020), the development, dissemination, and strict implementation of special education in schools must continue. To effectively provide education for all students with special educational needs and disabilities, inclusive education strategies and approaches must coexist with essential special education strategies and approaches. Hence, the problems with implementing inclusion are compounded by the need for more empirical research on the effectiveness of inclusion and stakeholders' awareness of the details of special education regulations. It suggested that everyone involved have a thorough understanding of special education regulations, be able to discriminate and understand history, and adopt the exact definition, standards, and goals when putting inclusion programs into action.

Findings by Sedláčková and Kantor (2022) showed that educators must comprehend how interpersonal relationships affect students' self-concept and personality development to create a healthy learning environment. Positive interactions in the classroom help students, especially those with special needs, develop a strong sense of identity, belonging, and self-worth. Educators prioritizing strong interpersonal relationships create a secure and welcoming environment where students feel appreciated, respected, and accepted, contributing to their social and emotional development and significantly impacting their personalities and self-concept.

Furthermore, Iswari and Murni (2020) stated that considering students' future goals and pathways while fostering an inclusive and supportive culture helps them succeed academically, socially, and emotionally. By preparing students for future opportunities and challenges, teachers can help them develop the confidence, resilience, and skills necessary to navigate the complexities of life beyond the classroom. Creating a friendly, inclusive environment that values healthy relationships guides students toward achievement, fulfillment, and overall well-being in every facet of their lives. Such environments nurture a supportive community where every student can thrive academically, socially, and emotionally.

Conclusion

5.1 Academic and Classroom-Related Struggles

Academic participation happens when the teacher created personalized lesson plans that addresses each student's unique needs and allows them to participate in the classroom more effectively. Ensure educational materials are easily accessed and customized to accommodate student needs and disabilities. Regardless of the type or level of their special education needs, students with disabilities are accommodated in general education classrooms due to the classrooms' adaptability.

5.2 Inclusive Environment and Peer Support

Provide students with easy access points for assistance sources, such as professional assistance, teacher guidance, or peer support. Help students develop their self-advocacy skills to express their needs and seek the right kind of help. Through self-advocacy, students with special needs may develop the ability to effectively address any rights abuses, pursue their interests, and understand their rights.

5.3 Teachers' Adjustment

Regular training should be conducted for teachers and students to encourage a setting that is more friendly and inclusive. Encourage parents, teachers, and students to collaborate to address problems, overcome challenges, and promote inclusivity. This issue highlights the importance to use inclusive education carefully and learning about inclusive education worldwide. Although essential lessons must be learned from the stories in this special issue, they must be appropriately applied.

5.4 Resilient and Supportive Community

Promote a strengths-based approach to education, emphasizing the potential and abilities of learners rather than their weaknesses. Encourage the development of mentorship programs that enable students to interact with adults who can guide, assist, and encourage them.

5.5 Adaptive Learning Strategies and Communication

Ensure that all students have access to the instructional technologies used in the classroom and that these tools are flexible enough to meet their individual needs and learning preferences. Teachers should also receive ongoing training on how to empower diverse learners via the use of technology. Applying digital technology in flexible learning environments enhances personalized learning, improving students' self-perceived ICT-related learning beliefs and self-reported digital skills. Develop school resource centers to support children with different learning needs and form interdisciplinary teams, including learners, counseling professionals, and researchers, to provide comprehensive assistance and guidance.

5.6 Motivation and Academic Improvement

To help learners efficiently address difficulties, incorporate activities that promote resilience, such as goal-setting workshops, mindfulness exercises, or reflection sessions. Promote a culture that promotes a growth mindset, in which failures are considered possibilities for improvement. Livelihood, academic, enrichment, pre-vocational, and care are learning areas intended to assist and prepare Filipino learners with special education needs to engage in entrepreneurship, further studies, or live functional lives.

5.7 Inclusive Education and Collaboration

Organize campaigns to promote the importance and benefits of inclusive education for all students within the school or community. Provide places or events to show gratitude and admiration to teachers who go above and beyond to help students in inclusive learning environments. Collaboration among stakeholders will be critical in creating a more inclusive environment. This joint effort will ensure that initiatives are cohesive and comprehensive. By working together, stakeholders can align their actions with the country's existing definitions, policies, and programs for inclusive education.

For students who are at risk of giving up, whether they have a disability or not, developing a sense of helplessness is a severe concern. Through prevention and intervention, each student has the potential to improve their self-perception and outlook on their achievements. One of the most vital things we can do to aid children in overcoming feelings of helplessness is to teach and engage with them in ways that nurture resilience.

As a teacher and the mother of a daughter with special needs, I connect deeply with certain aspects of their experiences. Although parenting a child with additional needs can be challenging, hearing the stories of the participants in this study inspired me to continue encouraging and empowering the development of other learners with disabilities. By conducting this research, I have the gift of hearing their tales of dedication and perseverance firsthand.

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